

An empirical analysis of Colombia's trade liberalisation and its effect on the equilibrium of its structural trade deficit.

Abstract

The article examines the extent to which Colombia's trade liberalisation, as a government strategy to boost its exports, has helped to balance its structural trade deficit. Based on the trade gravity model theory, we derive two-way specifications (Colombian exports and Colombian imports) in order to analyse bilateral trade flows (fuels and non-fuels) between Colombia and 136 countries from 2005-2018. Additionally, we compare the real export performance of Colombia with its main partners through the trade potential index (TPI), to assess the effect of Colombian openness on bilateral trade. The econometric approach indicates that the free trade agreement (FTA) factor has a negative net effect on Colombian exports and a positive net impact on Colombian imports. Finally, the TPI analysis allows us to infer that although there is an evolution towards the intensification of Colombian trade, this trend is greater in imports than in exports, which suggests a deepening of the Colombian trade deficit.

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1. Introduction

The past decade has witnessed the rapid development of trade liberalisation as one of the most critical policies in enhancing international trade around the world. In this regard, empirical research has explored the effects of the free trade agreement (FTA) factor on bilateral trade, showing that FTAs improve bilateral trade among associated countries (Egger *et al.*, 2011).

Colombia, as part of the Andean Community (AC) and one of the fastest-growing countries in the region, has developed a policy of trade openness in the last decades. This policy has been implemented through the signing of relevant trade agreements, which have different trade scopes and follow global trends in trade liberalisation.

However, there is no consensus about whether this process has had the expected effect on Colombian exports and its trade balance, and therefore, on domestic production and welfare.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the effects of the Colombian trade liberalization process and also to establish the impact of the signing of bilateral and regional trade agreements as an effective policy to reduce the deficit of the Colombian trade balance. Additionally, our study delves into the effect of FTAs on Colombian trade in fuel and non-fuel related goods, which allows us to determine the separate influence of FTAs on these types of products, which is essential due to the country's high dependence on its fuel exports. Furthermore, this study could be replicated in most of the Latin American countries, which are highly dependent on their commodity exports, as well as those countries whose exports depend particularly on fuels¹. Moreover, this study will allow us to analyse, through an empirical approach, the performance of the trade balance of a country which, on the one hand, largely depends on its fuel exports and, on the other hand, its oil reserves are about to run out. As far as we know, this is the first study that explores the determinants of Colombian international trade (export and import flow) by fuel and non-fuel flows. Consequently, the results of the study will allow us to suggest some trade policy recommendations focused on improving the efficiency of Colombia's trade openness.

Furthermore, we applied the trade gravity model to a cross-sectional dataset of bilateral exports to 136 countries from 2005 to 2018. Subsequently, this study sets out to assess the effects of a group of variables on exports between the parties, where the FTA factor stands out. Additionally, as is well known, a robust estimation of bilateral trade will allow us to compare the actual export performance of Colombia and its partners with the estimated export potential generated by the model through the trade potential index (TPI). This comparison will permit us to determine whether the signing of trade agreements by the Colombian governments has had the expected effect on trade. The research also considers two aspects of recent empirical analysis of international trade. The first is the fact of the presence of many zeros in bilateral trade data and the need to estimate the model with an approach more suitable than that of a traditional log-linear form; this approach is called the Poisson pseudo maximum likelihood (PPML) (Santos Silva and Teneyro, 2006). The second is the application of fixed effects to capture unobservable determinants in trade flows (Gopinath, Helpman, and Rogoff, 2014; WTO, 2012). Summing up, the proposed study will allow us to discern whether the Colombian trade liberalisation process has helped to balance its trade deficit.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 will describe the evolution of the Colombian trade liberalisation strategy in the last few decades through the international economic integration policy initially called *Apertura Comercial*. Section 3 and 4 are concerned with the methodological approach, and specification and data used for this study, respectively. Section 5 will offer the findings of the research, focusing on the effects of the variables involved in bilateral trade and the results of the TPI. As a final point, Section 6 and 7 will focus on discussion and additional concluding remarks.

¹ Fuel goods: Products from code 321.1 to code 351.0, according to the Standard International Trade Classification (SITC 3) (World Integrated Trade Solution, 2020).

2. Colombian Trade Liberalisation Process

Several authors state that trade liberalisation has a positive impact on economic growth (Manwa and Wijeweera, 2016). In this vein, Baier *et al.*, (2018) claim that more than 350 bilateral trade agreements have been notified to the World Trade Organisation (WTO) since 1986. Thus, there is evidence that the determination of the latest Colombian governments to develop a trade policy of international economic integration is associated with global trends, following what other countries had already done to promote their exports. This process, which has been encouraged by the promotion of international trade and investment relationships, has helped to create what Sokolov-Mladenović *et al.*, (2017) have called the global village. According to Lim and Breuer (2019), the pace of decreasing barriers to international trade has grown in the last 30 years, strongly reflected in developing countries to promote their economic growth.

The Colombian purpose of trade openness was embodied through membership of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT, lately WTO), reached on October 3, 1981 (WTO, 2019). The World Trade Organization has promoted the liberalisation of international trade during the last few decades through agreements signed by its member countries². More recently, continuing its process of international economic integration, Colombia joined the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2020 (OECD, 2020).

Nonetheless, the Colombian openness was sluggish until 1991. Since then, trade liberalisation was intensified, with the helping hand of the former president of the republic, Cesar Gaviria Trujillo. According to García *et al.*, (2014), Gaviria declared the intention of opening the economic system to make it more productive and efficient. To do so, an unprecedented set of reforms were implemented to promote what Gaviria called *Apertura Comercial*. Consequently, Colombia began negotiations to sign a significant number of bilateral and regional trade agreements.

In Colombian openness, two agreements stand out among the others. According to DANE (2019a), the Free Trade Agreement between Colombia and the United States of America (USA) and the Commercial Agreement between Colombia and the European Union (EU) are arrangements that, on average, have accounted for more than half of Colombian exports and imports from 2005 to 2018. Nonetheless, both agreements exhibit a deficit in the Colombian trade balance in the last years (MinCIT, 2018a). Likewise, it is essential to clarify that, although both markets are the most important, there is a big difference in trade amounts (MinCIT, 2018b), which is explained since the commercial relationship between Colombia and the USA has a more robust background. This is mostly elucidated by conditions such as their productive complementariness (most of Colombia's exports to the USA are oil, mining or agriculture goods. Unlike the USA exports, which are mostly goods with high added value); the income level of the USA citizens; the relatively short distance between the

² It is important to note that although WTO rounds have reduced trade barriers among nations, they took longer to institutionalise it than through bilateral or regional agreements (Lim and Breuer, 2019).

two countries; the degree of trade openness defined in their FTA; and their robust and historical cooperation in different and strategic areas for the Colombian economic development and social stability have also improved their bilateral relationship.

Another notable trade association for Colombia is the one reached with the Andean Community (AC), under the framework of a customs union. This agreement is highlighted by the fact that Colombian exports are mainly made up of manufactured products, unlike the USA and the EU. Colombian agreement with the AC is the oldest one signed by Colombia, and it is a natural market for national products due to its contiguity. According to the MinCIT (2018a), trade flows have had a continuous growth from 2001 to 2018, except for the slight drop registered in 2009. Likewise, trade relations with the AC countries reflect that, from 2001 to 2018, Colombia had a surplus in its trade balance, wherein a vast majority of exports are not from the oil or mining sectors. Particularly, Colombian exports to AC countries are mostly composed (72%) of goods from the basic and light industry. In contrast, imports from AC countries are mostly composed (65%) of raw materials, particularly agricultural products. This situation denotes, on the one hand, Colombia's specialisation in the production and export of manufactured goods, and on the other, the promotion of the production of value-added goods in commercial relations with the AC countries. Additionally, the trade flows show that Colombia and AC countries have a robust inter-industry trade pattern. However, it is essential to note that there is also intra-industry trade between them, mainly represented by machinery and transport equipment goods (Ramons and Toro, 2012). Nevertheless, trade agreements such as the Pacific Alliance, CARICOM and Mercosur have taken on greater commercial importance in recent years due to the notable increase in Colombian exports to these destinations.

Figure 1 presents Colombian export performance in millions of constant USD (base year = 2000) to the central destination countries by type of product from 2005 to 2018 in annual average figures.

Figure 1. Main world destinations of Colombian exports in millions of constant USD (base year = 2000) by type of product.

Source: Own elaboration based on the World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS) (2020). Deflated values based on the Export Price Index from Banco de la Republica (BanRep) (2020b).

Figure 1 shows that Colombian exports are mainly made up of fuels, and their relative importance in total exports continues to be noteworthy in each of the periods analysed. Particularly, Colombian exports to the USA represent about a third of the total Colombian exports in every period shown, clarifying the significance of the USA market. Furthermore, exports show an expansionary trend with countries with which a trade agreement is in force. Those countries are Ecuador, Mexico, Brazil, Spain and even Chile, although the latter exhibits a slight reduction in the last period. However, according to Figure 1, the highest export growth rates occur with countries with which there is no signed trade agreement: China, Panama and Turkey. In this regard, Colombian exports have seen an outstanding performance with China, explained by the growth in its consumption of oil and mining goods. These types of exports represented 93.8% of Colombian exports to China in 2018 (MinCIT, 2020). Moreover, it is important to note that there is a trade agreement already signed with Panama and the legislative bodies of both countries are processing its approval, and also, that another trade agreement is under negotiation with Turkey (MinCIT, 2019a).

On the other hand, Figure 2 presents Colombian import performance in millions of constant USD (base year = 2000) from the central origin countries by type of product from 2005 to 2018 in annual average figures.

Figure 2. Main world origins of Colombian imports in millions of constant USD (base year = 2000) by type of product.

Source: Own elaboration based on WITS (2020). Deflated values based on the Import Price Index from BanRep (2020b).

In Figure 2, it is seen that the USA is the primary origin of Colombian imports. Nonetheless, this scenario may change shortly due to the notable increase in imports from China. Additionally, remarkable growth in

Colombian imports with most of the countries is appreciated. Unlike exports, Colombian imports are made up almost entirely of non-fuel³ goods. However, it is important to mention that the USA is a prominent supplier of refined petroleum products such as gasoline and light oils (DANE, 2019b). Furthermore, it is needed to state that even with a profound devaluation of the Colombian peso 42.3% between 2005 and 2018 (BanRep, 2020a), imports have had an upward trend. Moreover, Colombian international trade has been strongly influenced by the international price oscillation of fuels goods; this is explained because according to MinCIT (2018b), 63.3% of Colombian exports were composed by those types of products. This fact creates a substantial influence on the terms of trade, causing a constant and notable fluctuation in the exchange rate (USD/COL). It is important to note that, although there is a general assumption about the symmetric effect of exchange rate changes on the trade balance (depreciation improves the trade balance and appreciation worsens it), this assumption is not so simple as is adequately explained through the concept of asymmetric J-curve (Bahmani-Oskooee *et al.*, 2019). Nonetheless, Bahmani-Oskooee *et al.* (2018) found that depreciation provokes an increase in price competitiveness and exports in the short run, but this positive effect must be accompanied by other measures such as an adequate monetary policy to have a long-term effect.

Considering all of this evidence, it seems that Colombian exports have an explicit dependence on the fuel industry. Regarding this, Karabulut *et al.* (2020) in their study on the effect of global economic uncertainties on commodity prices, affirm that certain shocks such as the recent trade wars have increased their price volatility which can eventually generate lower growth for commodity producing dependend countries such as Colombia. Additionally, although the growth of non-fuel exports has been remarkable, an oil export substitution scenario is not feasible in the short term under current economic conditions. Moreover, the Colombian trade performance evidenced a deepening of its trade balance deficit, especially in the last period analysed. It is imperative to highlight that the trade deficit scenario was intensified after the signing of some of the most outstanding FTAs, questioning their effectiveness to reduce its deficit. Hence, it suggests that the income elasticity of imports appears to be greater than that of exports, which reveals the deterioration in terms of trade reflected in the expansion of the Colombian trade deficit. Finally, although the Colombian trade openness has had a positive influence on Colombian exports, the positive effect has been more significant on Colombian imports, deepening the deficit in the country's trade balance.

3. Methodological approach

To assess the determinants of Colombian trade flows, a robust and successful econometric method is implemented: the trade gravity model. The technique is commonly used in empirical studies to consider the factors that explain international trade among countries. Furthermore, it is a very good fit to predict bilateral trade flows, and this property has been recognised in many papers (Fally, 2015). The model is proposed based on the theory called the *Law of Universal Gravity* of the English physicist Sir Isaac Newton (Abidin *et al.*,

³ Other products than those indicated as fuels.

2013). For Bergstrand (1985), the gravity equation states that trade between two countries can be explained by the economic forces of trade in the country of origin and by the economic forces of trade in the country of destination, and, additionally, through the economic forces that help or resist the flow of trade from origin to destination. Guo and Guo (2015) state that the volume of trade between two economies is directly proportional to the product of their economic masses, defined by the GDPs, and inversely proportional to the physical distance between them.

Consistent with Anderson (1979), the gravity equation ordinarily is specified as:

$$X_{ij} = \alpha_o Y_i^{\alpha_1} Y_j^{\alpha_2} D_{ij}^{\alpha_3} n_{ij}$$

where X_{ij} denotes trade flows between country i to country j , Y_i and Y_j denote the country incomes defined by their GDPs and D_{ij} denotes the distance between i and j . Furthermore, the equation includes all the factors that might create resistance to trade. Likewise, n_{ij} represents an error factor statistically independent of the regressors. Finally, $\alpha_o, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ are unknown parameters.

The first developments of the gravity model for the study of international trade were formulated by Tinbergen (1962) and Poyhonen (1963). They analysed the pattern of bilateral trade among European countries. Anderson (1979) claimed that the gravity equation was probably the most successful mechanism for the empirical study of international trade, although, at that time, part of its theoretical justification had not been identified. Deardorff (1984) affirmed that, despite this initial criticism in theory, the gravity model has become popular due to its empirical success in predicting bilateral trade flows of various commodities in different situations. The theoretical justification of the gravity model was mainly made by Anderson and van Wincoop (2003), where it was recognised that the prediction of the gravity model could be derived from the Ricardian approach, the Heckscher-Ohlin-Samuelson model and the New Theory of Trade based on increasing returns to scale (Gopinath *et al.*, 2014; Kabir, Salim, and Al-Mawali, 2017).

Furthermore, one of the most critical advances in the gravity model was the introduction of Multilateral Resistance Terms (MRT), a progress that was popularised by Anderson and van Wincoop (2003). They showed that controlling relative trade costs is crucial for a well-specified gravity model. Additionally, their theoretical results showed that bilateral trade is determined by relative trade costs (WTO, 2012). Furthermore, this statement was already supported by Krugman (1995), who stated that bilateral distance is a crucial empirical element in bilateral trade, and added that this could not be the sole factor that matters in the gravity equation.

Another important key in the development of the gravity model was the introduction of the Fixed Effects. They are implemented to capture unobservable MRT in trade flows. Country-pair fixed effects are useful when econometric models lack plausible instrumental variables (Gopinath *et al.*, 2014). Likewise, they are useful when there are specific MRTs that affect trade between a pair of countries, but not with third parties (WTO, 2012). Moreover, individual country fixed effects effectively absorb all bilateral trade frictions, including any unobservable component of trade costs, which otherwise would enter the error term and potentially lead to

inconsistent estimates (Baier *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, Gopinath *et al.* (2014) mention that these effects are used to control systematic tendencies to export or import large relative amounts to its GDP and other observed trade determinants. Due to that, any unobservable determinants that contribute to change the overall level of exports or imports of a country will be taken into account. Lastly, time-variant fixed effects suit a database that spans many years.

4. Specification and Data

In the empirical study, 136 countries were selected. These countries were the destination of 99% of the Colombian exports in 2018 (DANE, 2019a). The period analysed was between 2005 and 2018. The study period was chosen taking into account that since 2005 the Colombian trade integration process has been intensified through the signing of trade agreements, and until 2018 due to the implementation of the latest economic data available at the time the research was complete.

The variables implemented in the model vary in economic, historical, geographical and trade characteristics. The specification follows the variable selection process made by Egger *et al.* (2011), which was adapted to our research, and contain elements exhibited in Table 1.

Table 1. Information of variables implemented in the model.

Variable	Description	Update date	Source	Expected sign
$X_{Total\ Colj}$	Colombian exports to its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$M_{Total\ jCol}$	Colombian imports from its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$X_{Fuels\ Colj}$	Colombian fuel exports to its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$M_{Fuels\ jCol}$	Colombian fuel imports from its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$X_{Non-fuels\ Colj}$	Colombian non-fuel exports to its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$M_{Non-fuels\ jCol}$	Colombian non-fuel imports from its partners in constant USD	June 19, 2020	World Integrated Trade Solution	
$LogDIST_{Colj}$	Log Distance in kilometres between Colombia to country j	March 30, 2019	CEPII	-
$CONTIG_{Colj}$	Common physical border between Colombia and country j	March 30, 2019	CEPII	+

<i>COMLANG_{Colj}</i>	Colombia and country <i>j</i> share a common legal language that is spoken by at least 9% of the population of both countries	March 30, 2019	CEPII	+
<i>COLONY_{Colj}</i>	Colombia and country <i>j</i> ever in colonial relationship	March 30, 2019	CEPII	+
<i>LogGDP_j</i>	Log GDP of Colombian partner in constant USD	July 1, 2019	World Bank	+
<i>WTO_j</i>	Colombian partner is a member of the WTO	March 30, 2019	CEPII	+
<i>OECD_j</i>	Colombian partner is a member of the OECD	June 30, 2020	OECD	+
<i>FTA_{Colj}</i>	Colombia and country <i>j</i> with Free Trade Agreement in force	May 8, 2019	WTO	+

Source: Own elaboration.

Consequently, six econometric specifications that follow the approach of Egger *et al.* (2011) are proposed to analyse, on the one hand, total export flows and export flows by type of products (fuels and non-fuels) from Colombia to its partners. On the other hand, the total import flows and the import flows by type of products (fuels and non-fuels) from the Colombian partners to Colombia.

The first three econometric specifications include time fixed effects captured by δ_t , time-invariant country fixed effects in the destination captured by α_j and an identical set of explanatory variables. Model (1) represents the estimation for total Colombian exports to its partners, Model (2) for Colombian fuel exports, and Model (3) for Colombian non-fuel exports and are denoted by X_{Coljt} .

Export models:

$$X_{Coljt} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogDIST}_{Colj} + \beta_2 \text{CONTIG}_{Colj} + \beta_3 \text{COLONY}_{Colj} + \beta_4 \text{COMLANG}_{Colj} + \beta_5 \text{LogGDP}_{jt} + \beta_6 \text{WTO}_{jt} + \beta_7 \text{OECD}_{jt} + \beta_8 \text{FTA}_{Coljt} + \delta_t + \alpha_j) n_{Coljt} \quad (1)$$

The remaining econometric specifications also include time fixed effects captured by α_t , time-invariant country fixed effects in origin captured by α_j and an identical set of explanatory variables. In these models, the dependant variable varies from total imports from Colombian partners in model (4), to fuel imports from Colombian partners in model (5) and non-fuel imports from Colombian partners in model (6) and are denoted by X_{Coljt} .

Import models:

$$M_{jCott} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogDIST}_{jCol} + \beta_2 \text{CONTIG}_{jCol} + \beta_3 \text{COLONY}_{jCol} + \beta_4 \text{COMLANG}_{jCol} + \beta_5 \text{LogGDP}_{jt} + \beta_6 \text{WTO}_{jt} + \beta_7 \text{OECD}_{jt} + \beta_8 \text{FTA}_{jCott} + \delta_t + \alpha_j) n_{jCott} \quad (2)$$

Additionally, the latest studies have proposed to estimate gravity models in multiplicative form instead of the usual log-linear estimation. Santos Silva and Teneyro (2006) recommend Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) as a more suitable estimator in gravity models. They claim that this estimator is robust to different patterns of heteroskedasticity, providing a natural way to deal with zero values of the dependent variable when there are many elements and offer identical weight to the observations. In this regard, they noted that although there are pairs of countries that do not trade in some years (zero values), their inclusion in the gravity equation in its multiplicative form (PPML) does not pose problems, but it does strengthen the estimate and therefore the results of the study. Frankel (1997) described the different ways to deal with zero values in gravity models when a log-linear method is used in the estimations, nonetheless, all of these procedures lead to inconsistent parameters of interest. Additionally, estimating with PPML instead of OLS makes a difference in the size of the coefficients. They state that the PPML estimator offers smaller and more suitable results in variables such as distance, colony, contiguity, trade agreements among others than those provided by the OLS estimator. The authors also state that the PPML approach does not provide evidence of incorrect specification or puzzling results generated by the other approaches, which allows them to claim that the empirical methods conventionally used to estimate gravity equations are inappropriate. Considering all these facts, Fally (2015) affirms that more trust should be given to those gravity model estimates that implement the PPML method. Gopinath *et al.* (2014) state that the differences in the coefficient are due to the existence of a non-linear effect in the distance and, therefore, OLS estimate a more substantial trade for large economies and reduces trade for small economies. Moreover, Fally (2015) states that the PPML estimator leads to a perfect fit between the fixed effects and their MRT. Regarding MRTs, Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) state that the traditional trade gravity model is incorrectly specified because this does not take into account MRTs, which can be solved with the inclusion of exporter and importer fixed effects. However, it is important to note that, in some very specific and rare circumstances, the estimation results can be improved using country pair effects (WTO, 2012). Given this, the models proposed in this study are estimated with the PPML approach, exporter or importer time-invariant fixed effects (depending on the model) to account for MRTs and time fixed effects because the panel covers many years.

5. Results

Table 3 presents the results of the six proposed models based on the data described in section 4.

Table 3. Estimation results

Variables	Exports			Imports		
	Total	Fuels	Non-fuels	Total	Fuels	Non-fuels
<i>LogDIST_{Colj}</i>	-1.450***	-1.856***	-0.956***	-0.212	-4.088***	0.002

	(0.314)	(0.403)	(0.147)	(0.372)	(1.052)	(0.319)
<i>CONTIG</i> _{Colj}	0.094	-0.689	0.840***	0.249	-4.012**	0.549
	(0.446)	(0.760)	(0.255)	(0.540)	(1.804)	(0.488)
<i>COMLANG</i> _{Colj}	0.385	0.047	0.803***	0.763	-1.062	0.879*
	(0.426)	(0.578)	(0.226)	(0.473)	(1.420)	(0.455)
<i>COLONY</i> _{Colj}	0.583	1.262**	-0.459**	-0.465	0.751	-0.514
	(0.370)	(0.552)	(0.194)	(0.486)	(1.290)	(0.483)
<i>LogGDP</i> _j	0.813***	0.920***	0.721***	0.997***	1.470***	0.976***
	(0.097)	(0.152)	(0.058)	(0.112)	(0.250)	(0.117)
<i>WTO</i> _j	-0.465	-0.931	0.884**	1.874***	-1.823	2.286***
	(0.667)	(0.683)	(0.393)	(0.455)	(1.386)	(0.469)
<i>OECD</i> _j	0.235	0.349	0.237	-0.820*	-0.279	-0.777*
	(0.555)	(0.790)	(0.331)	(0.446)	(1.064)	(0.455)
<i>FTA</i> _{Colj}	-0.331*	-1.131***	0.373***	0.486***	0.699**	0.477***
	(0.180)	(0.362)	(0.118)	(0.160)	(0.301)	(0.182)
<i>Constant</i>	10.236***	11.068***	5.787***	-7.313**	13.711***	-9.191***
	(3.232)	(3.861)	(1.720)	(3.344)	(3.020)	(3.065)
Observations	1,870	1,870	1,870	1,870	1,870	1,870
R²	0.846	0.752	0.909	0.894	0.911	0.884
Countries	136	136	136	136	136	136
Time-invariant country fixed effects	X	X	X	X	X	X
Time fixed effects	X	X	X	X	X	X
Notes: Robust standard errors in parentheses. These are based on robust standard errors that have been adjusted for clustering by country pair.						
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1						

Concerning the models that estimate Colombian exports to the world, they reflect some interesting results. In line with the theoretical and empirical approach, the distance factor harms exports. Likewise, according to the trade gravity model theory, the GDP of Colombian partners has a substantial effect on Colombian exports in each model. Additionally, control variables such as contiguity, common language, and colony, are statistically significant only for the non-fuel model, except for the latter variable, which is also significant in the fuel estimate. Furthermore, if a Colombian partner is a member of the WTO, Colombian non-fuel exports will increase considerably. Conversely, the variable corresponding to whether a Colombian partner is part of the

OECD is insignificant in every model. Finally, regarding total exports, the coefficient reveals that when Colombia share an FTA with its partners, its total exports decrease by 28.2%. In the same vein, when Colombia share an FTA with its partners, its fuel exports decrease by 67.7%. However, if Colombia shares an FTA with its partners, its non-fuel exports grow by 45.2%.

Regarding the models that estimate Colombian imports from the world, some differences are observed concerning the previous specifications. The distance variable is significant only in the fuel imports model, and its effect is large and negative on these flows. Additionally, the GDP of Colombian partners reflect that their magnitudes impact Colombian imports positively and substantially in every specification. About the control variables, the contiguity factor negatively and significantly affects fuel imports. Colony tie is insignificant in these models. Furthermore, if a Colombian partner is a member of the WTO, total and non-fuels Colombian imports from these origins will increase considerably. Moreover, if the Colombian partner is a member of the OECD, total and non-fuel Colombian imports from these origins will be reduced. Additionally, the effect of an FTA between the parties on the models is positive, although its magnitude differs in each model. Particularly, its effect on total imports will expand their flows to Colombia by 62.6%, by 101.2% on fuel imports, and by 61.6% on non-fuel imports.

Furthermore, related to the remarkable effect of the FTA factor on non-fuel exports and non-fuel imports, we performed a hypothesis testing for means. Regarding the bilateral trade of non-fuel goods, the test result confirms that the difference between the two parameters is significantly different from zero. The test also confirms that the effect of the FTA on non-fuel imports is higher than on non-fuel exports with a level of statistical significance of 99%. This information allows us to infer that although the FTA has a significant influence on Colombian non-fuel trade flows, the effect is greater in the case of these imports, which is in line with the regression values. The hypothesis testing for means was also performed for total exports and total imports. The test result confirms that the difference between the two parameters is also significantly different from zero. The result also confirms that the positive effect of the FTA parameter on total imports is higher than the negative effect of this parameter on total exports with a level of statistical significance of 99%. Both test results suggest a deepening of the deficit in Colombia's trade balance and, therefore, an eventual impact on its economic growth.

Accordingly, the models are robust and fit well enough to use the predicted trade volumes of this model as a benchmark for discussing the potential trade of Colombia with its partners, and *vice versa*, through the trade potential index (TPI). According to Egger (2012), TPI is calculated through the residual values of the estimated gravity equation. Hence, the TPI ratio is obtained by calculating the difference between the observed and the predicted values.

De Benedictis and Vicarelli (2005) calculate the TPI through the following ratio:

$$TPI_i = \frac{\hat{x}_{ijt}}{x_{ijt}}$$

where X_{ijt} is the observed value of exports from country i to country j , and \hat{X}_{ijt} is the estimated value of exports generated by the gravity model. Then the TPI is standardised so that the index takes values between -1 and 1 :

$$TPI_i = \frac{TP_i - 1}{TP_i + 1}$$

Positive values of TPI between 0 and 1 show an under-trading situation, while negative values between -1 and 0 show an over-trading situation.

In this study, TPI is calculated for 2005 and 2018, taking into consideration that the Colombian trade integration process was intensified since 2005. and 2018 as the most recent year of available data.

Colombian TPI with its main partners is computed for every model proposed, and this is presented in the following table.

Table 4. Colombian TPI with its main partners.

Country	Total		Fuels		Non-fuels	
	2005	2018	2005	2018	2005	2018
Brazil	0.70	0.14	0.78	-0.75	0.66	0.02
Chile	-0.29	-0.45	-0.22	-0.63	-0.36	-0.27
China	-0.07	-0.59	N.A.	-0.57	-0.32	-0.34
Ecuador	-0.49	-0.17	-0.74	0.10	-0.22	-0.27
Mexico	0.16	0.16	0.06	0.16	0.31	0.10
Panama	0.22	-0.28	0.22	-0.48	0.20	0.27
Spain	0.38	0.05	0.65	0.01	-0.10	0.01
Turkey	-0.04	-0.64	-0.48	-0.66	0.80	0.65
USA	-0.08	0.09	-0.11	0.10	-0.10	0.07

Source: Own elaboration based on TPI estimations.

Model (1) reflects that, in terms of total exports, Colombia has an over-trading situation with the majority of its main partners (Chile, China, Ecuador, Panama, and Turkey), a situation that has deepened in 2018. Likewise, its under-trading situation is decreasing with some of its partners (Brazil and Spain). This situation suggests that Colombian exports to these countries have grown more than the estimated by the model according to the proposed specification, reflecting the intensification of Colombian exports with these countries (see Figure 1). Conversely, the Colombian TPI level with the USA has increased during the same period. This is explained by the contraction of Colombian exports after the entry into force of their FTA (see Figure 1). On the other hand, Model (2) exhibits that, in terms of fuel exports, Colombia has notably reduced its TPI with most of its partners (Brazil, Chile, China, Panama, Spain, and Turkey). Nonetheless, the Colombian TPI has experienced an expansion with countries such as Ecuador, Mexico and the USA. Concerning Ecuador, this is explained by the fact that Colombian fuel exports to Ecuador have remained relatively stable in the last period. About the USA,

fuel products exported to this destiny have been partially replaced by non-fuel exports. Regarding Mexico, Colombian fuel exports to this destination have grown, although their growth rate has been lower compared to the advance of non-fuel exports. Furthermore, Model (3) shows that, in terms of non-fuel exports, Colombia has seen a reduction of its TPI with its partners (Brazil, China, Ecuador, Mexico, Spain, and Turkey), some of which already reflected an over-trading situation. This is due to the notable growth of its non-fuel exports to these countries and the subsequent reduction of its export potential. However, the Colombian TPI with countries such as Chile, to which Colombia has increased its non-fuel exports and has reduced its fuel exports; Panama, where the largest proportion of Colombian exports are fuels, and the USA, where non-fuel exports have gained relative importance compared to fuel exports, reflect an expansion in the Colombian TPI in the period analysed.

Furthermore, TPI for main Colombian partners with Colombia is computed to every model proposed and is presented in the following table.

Table 5. Main Colombian partners TPI with Colombia.

Country	Total		Fuels		Non-fuels	
	2005	2018	2005	2018	2005	2018
Brazil	-0.09	-0.18	-0.26	-0.60	-0.05	-0.15
China	-0.08	-0.32	-0.74	-0.11	-0.06	-0.32
France	0.11	0.01	-0.68	0.35	0.13	-0.02
Germany	-0.12	-0.15	0.68	0.76	-0.13	-0.19
India	0.30	0.10	0.82	-0.29	0.33	0.11
Japan	0.16	0.04	-0.72	0.76	0.20	0.06
Mexico	-0.37	-0.48	0.91	-0.27	-0.44	-0.50
Spain	0.03	-0.07	0.84	0.47	0.05	-0.07
USA	0.06	0.16	0.29	-0.04	0.03	0.20

Source: Own elaboration based on TPI estimations.

Model (4) shows that, in terms of total Colombian imports, every partner has reduced their TPI level with the nation, except for the USA, although the latter's exports to Colombia are growing at a remarkable rate (see Figure 2). The evolution of Colombian partners TPI reflects that openness has boosted the Colombian imports above the model's predictions. Additionally, Model (5) exhibits that, in terms of Colombian fuel imports, the TPI level of the Colombian partners with Colombia present diverse performances. Nonetheless, it is essential to state that of the partners presented, only the USA and Mexico export fuels to Colombia. In both cases, it is seen a noteworthy reduction of their TPI level with Colombia, although the USA reflects an increase in its fuel exports to Colombia in each period and Mexico presents a small decline in the last period (see Figure 2). Furthermore, Model (6) reveals that, in terms of Colombian non-fuel imports, the TPI performance of its partners have been similar to that observed in Model (4). This trend shows that openness has boosted the Colombian non-fuel imports above the model's predictions.

In summary, the data obtained allow us to infer that, in general, the TPI of Colombia with its partners and the TPI of Colombian partners with Colombia reflect a trend towards the intensification of the over-trading situation or towards to achievement of this status. The evolution of Colombian trade flows (both exports and imports) in the period studied confirms the presence of the trend towards the over-trading. However, there is higher growth in its import flows than in its export flows. Considering this, the consolidation of that trend over time would lead the country to suffer an intense exchange rate crisis due to a deepening of the deficit in the national trade balance. Additionally, if we complement this trend with the expected depletion of fuel products in the short term (Presidency of the Republic of Colombia, 2020), the economic problems generated by the probable exchange rate crisis would be harmful for the Colombian economy.

6. Discussion

The proposed trade gravity model approach exhibits the influence of Colombia's trade integration processes on its bilateral trade, primarily through the signing of FTAs. Remarkably, most of the parameter values are consistent with similar latest studies (Baier *et al.*, 2018; Egger *et al.*, 2011; Fally, 2015; Melitz and Toubal, 2019; Santos Silva and Teneyro, 2006).

Firstly, we want to highlight that the distance coefficient is not as large as in other studies (Santos Silva and Teneyro, 2006). This is explained by the fact that we estimate the models through the PPML approach. However, the impact of the distance on bilateral trade is still high and adverse in the majority of the models. Despite all the improvements in transport, freights packaging, insurance and the like, the distance variable continues to be one of the critical factors that explain the volume of bilateral trade.

Regarding models that estimate Colombian exports, it is appreciated that its trade openness has promoted the achievement of some objectives, for instance, the partial substitution of fuel exports by non-fuel exports. This encouraging effect is exhibited in the Colombian non-fuel export performance, where substantial growth in these exports is observed. Similarly, it is appreciated a notable influence on Colombian non-fuel exports if a destination country is a member of the WTO. Additionally, it is reflected that the effect of the FTA variable on total and fuel exports is adverse, and this effect is more prominent in fuel than in total exports. The negative effect of the FTA variable on Colombian exports is contrary to that found by similar studies (Ahcar, 2018; Cárdenas and García, 2005; Serrano *et al.*, 2015). The findings show that, on the one hand, Colombian trade openness has helped promote non-fuel exports and, on the other hand, the amount of fuel exports has decreased with some partners. Nevertheless, due to the high dependence on fuel exports, the Colombian government should create an effective policy to promote non-fuel exports due to the reduced reserves of fuel-related products in the following years (Presidencia de la Republica de Colombia, 2020). Therefore, if Colombian policymakers fail to replace fuel exports, the deepening of the trade balance deficit will damage the local currency to such a level that the Colombian peso may experience an unprecedented devaluation, affecting the entire economy.

About the models that estimate Colombian imports, trade openness has helped to promote Colombian imports substantially. The promotion is especially evident in the specifications for total and non-fuel imports. Notably, models for total and non-fuel imports reveal that distance is insignificant in these flows. This suggests that transportation costs do not restrict them, which explains why countries such as China and India are large suppliers of the country. In contrast, the model for fuel imports reflects that distance is a factor that profoundly and negatively affects fuel exports to Colombia. This explains that most of these imports come from nearby markets. However, having a common border with Colombia restricts its fuel exports. The situation implies that these exports are made by nearby countries with which a common border is not shared, such as the USA and Mexico (see Figure 2). Concerning the FTA factor in Colombian imports, its positive effect can be seen in every model with a predominance on non-fuel imports. Likewise, it is essential to highlight that if the Colombian partners belong to the WTO, their total exports and their non-fuel exports to Colombia tend to grow significantly. Nonetheless, if the Colombian partners belong to the OECD, their exports of the same type of products to Colombia will be affected negatively, the opposite result than expected.

In accordance with the present results, we could affirm that there is a clear trend towards a deepening of the Colombian trade balance not only in the present-day but also in the future. These results are contrary to those found by Quansah and Ahn (2017), who in their study of sectorial trade found that the signing of the bilateral trade agreement between Korea and Australia contributed to balance their bilateral trade. The deficit situation is reflected in the notable difference between the values of the FTA parameters generated for exports and imports. The results of the hypothesis testing for means performed for total exports and non-fuel exports also confirm this tendency. These results suggest a greater influence of the FTA parameter on imports than on exports for the models referred, confirming the trend towards a deepening trade deficit. In this regard, it would be interesting to inquire about the degree of complementarity that Colombia and its trading partners have, taking into account the results obtained in this respect by Vahálík (2014). Additionally, this trade deficit tendency is also easily perceived through the evolution of Colombian bilateral trade in recent years, confirming once again the expansion of the Colombian trade deficit and the very likely damage to its economy in the long term.

Regarding the TPI of Colombia with its partners, the proposed models reveal a general trend towards an over-trading situation with most of its partners, although its performance varies in relation to the model analysed. The results of the Colombian TPI allow us to identify a defined pattern with some of its strategic partners in every model proposed. For instance, the Colombian TPI with the USA reveals a trend towards an expansion of its under-trading situation, and this is evidenced in the notable decline in Colombian exports to the USA. Moreover, the Colombian TPI with China reflects a remarkable trend towards the intensification of its over-trading situation, which is reflected in a notable increase in its exports to this country. Likewise, there is a significant trend towards an over-trading situation with countries such as Brazil, Chile and Turkey. However, if the analysis focuses on the type of products, it is observed that there is a general trend towards an over-trading situation on fuel exports, unlike non-fuel exports, where there is no defined general trend. These deductions allow us to affirm that although Colombian liberalisation has had a positive impact on non-fuel exports, which is reflected in a general trend towards an over-trading situation, the evolution of total exports has been affected

mainly by the reduction of fuel exports to the USA and this reduction has not been balanced by the growth in non-fuel exports.

Concerning the TPI of the Colombian partners with Colombia, the models reflect an evident trend towards over-trading situation than that reflected in the Colombian TPI. This trend is mainly reflected in the models of total and non-fuel imports since fuel imports are relatively low and come principally from Mexico and the USA. However, a strategic supplier for Colombia such as the USA shows a trend towards an under-trading situation in the total and non-fuel imports models and a trend towards an over-trading situation in the fuel imports model, which is evidenced in a considerable increase of Colombian imports from this country (see Figure 2). Conversely, the other Colombian supplier countries analysed reflect a clear trend towards an over-trade situation in total and non-fuel imports (see Table 5), a tendency that is reflected in the strengthening of Colombian imports (see Figure 2). This scenario allows us to sustain that the Colombian openness has been successful for Colombian partners due to the manifest tendency to the over-trading situation reflected by most of the TPIs of its partners. This is also confirmed through the notable increase in Colombian imports from each of its analysed partners.

These findings suggest that the impact of Colombian trade liberalisation carried out mainly through the signing of the FTA has deepened the deficit in its trade balance. Regarding this, as noted by Thirlwall (1979) in the balance of payments constrained growth theory (BPCG), international trade can drive long-term growth through the interaction between trade and growth. Therefore, long-term growth will occur if national products are more attractive to foreigners and if foreign products are less attractive to nationals; or through increased global growth (Setterfield, 2012). Consequently, our findings indicate a breach of what was indicated by Thirlwall since the objective of balancing the Colombian trade deficit, and eventually, reaching a trade surplus through trade openness, has not been achieved, which calls into question the future economic growth of Colombia under these circumstances. In the same vein, it is essential to remark that the expected increase in bilateral trade between Colombia and its main partners through the signing of FTAs, and the consequent liberalisation of trade between the parties, was not as expected, at least for Colombian exports. Finally, our findings on FTA factor contrasts with the results obtained in other studies, where a positive value of the FTA parameter is predominant (Anderson and Yotov, 2011; Baier and Bergstrand, 2009; Egger *et al.*, 2011; Santos Silva and Teneyro, 2006).

7. Concluding remarks

In this paper, the authors wish to present the results of a gravity model approach applied to evaluate the trade performance by type of products between Colombia and its principal partners from 2005 to 2018. The study yields insights into the trade effects created by the Colombian trade openness and the TPI is implemented to assess its influence.

Although as mentioned, the global effect of the FTA for total Colombian exports with its partners is adverse, the analysis of its effect by type of goods yields two different outcomes. On the one hand, It is observed that an

FTA in force between Colombia and its partners reduces the fuel exports of the former, and these tend to be partially replaced, although to a lesser extent, by non-fuel exports. This effect is in line with one of the purposes of Colombian trade policy: the substitution of fuel exports for non-fuel exports, which has been promoted through numerous government programs to boost exports of non-fuel goods (Procolombia, 2020). It should be noted that this purpose of Colombian trade policy is strategic to support the dynamism of the country's exports because, in a recent report of the Presidency of the Republic of Colombia (2020), it is stated that proven oil reserves are claimed to amount to 2,036 million barrels in 2019, placing an estimated production for 6.3 years. Furthermore, concerning non-fuel exports, a noticeable positive influence is observed in their promotion if Colombian partners are members of the WTO. Its effect is much more intense than that created through the signed of bilateral or regional trade agreements framed in the FTA factor.

On the other hand, Colombian imports from its partners have been promoted by the signing of FTAs with Colombia. It is not only observed in the progress of their performance but the notable effect of the FTA variable in the regressions. Unlike Colombian exports, the encouraging effect of an FTA on Colombian imports prevails in each estimate. Additionally, the effect of being a member of the WTO for non-fuel imports is prominent. Moreover, if we compare the values of the FTA parameter and its influence on Colombian exports and imports, particularly of total goods and non-fuel goods through the results of the hypothesis test for means, a clear trend towards a deepening of the Colombian trade deficit is expected.

Additionally, the reduction of the Colombian TPI with its main partners, reflected in the proposed specifications, shows that the country should diversify its export destinations. Subsequently, the country should analyse the viability of deepening its trade integration with countries with which there is no traditional integration process, through integration mechanisms other than the FTAs. Likewise, the possibility of deepening the agreements already established with some of its partners through the signing of new agreements could be studied, as is the case of the Pacific Alliance agreement. This policy has boosted Colombian exports to the member countries of the alliance, with which Colombia previously had a trade agreement. Furthermore, although the evolution of the Colombian TPI with its main partners shows a trend towards an over-trading situation, this is not reflected in the expected increase in national exports. On the contrary, the same trend reflected in the TPI of the Colombian partners with Colombia is established in a higher relative increase in Colombian imports from their main partners. These facts reveal that the Colombian trade liberalisation process has intensified the deficit in its trade balance. According to DANE (2019a), the Colombian trade balance with most of these countries has become a deficit during the last period proposed (2015-2018). Consequently, these deductions question the Colombian trade liberalisation policy focused on the signing of new trade agreements as an effective measure to increase its exports, and therefore, reduce its trade deficit.

Furthermore, as noted, the Colombian trade pattern is mainly dependent on fuel goods, which means trading goods with little or no added value, and, also, their prices and consumption depend on exogenous factors. In this regard, it is observed that the signing of trade agreements has partially supported the substitution of fuel exports for non-fuel exports, although the amount of this substitution has not offset the fall in fuel exports.

Therefore, more considerable efforts are needed to ensure proper conversion of Colombian's trade pattern. This challenge must be complemented by effective trade policies that promote the competitiveness of Colombian companies in global sceneries. For instance, although Colombia has seen its trade potential with its main partners reduced, its TPI with some countries is superior to others. Consequently, the Colombian government should create public policies that guide companies to trade with more suitable country destinations to take advantage of its TPI situation.

Finally, although our econometric approach contradicts the effect of other studies regarding the positive influence of the signing of FTAs, as is the case with total and fuel Colombian exports, it is observed that the effect of this factor on non-fuel exports is reached. Similarly, this positive effect is achieved by Colombian imports, regardless of the type of goods. Likewise, our findings reflect that the expected effect of boosting Colombian exports through trade openness, and consequently reducing the deficit in its trade balance, has not been reached, on the contrary, the deficit tends to expand. Hence, this information can be used to develop public interventions aimed at boosting Colombian trade beyond the development of a trade policy focused on the signing of new trade agreements. These policies should be addressed at strengthening a more competitive national production, which promotes its exports and discourages its imports, to balance its trade deficit and promote its long-term growth (Thirlwall, 1979). Finally, future research should be focused on determining the reasons why this expected positive effect has not been adequately achieved in the Colombian trade liberalisation process, evidenced in the structural and ascendant deficit of the Colombian trade balance.

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